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¹ The term ‘project’ used in this report equates to an ‘action’ in certain other Horizon 2020 documentation

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Table of abbreviations

AIT	Austrian Institute of Technology
API	Advanced Programming Interface
CWTS	Center for Science and Technology Studies, University of Leiden
EEA	European Economic Area
EFTA	European Free Trade Agreement
ERA	European Research Area
ESID	European Social Innovation Database
EU-FP	European Framework Programs
HEI	Higher Education Institutions
KET	Key Enabling Technologies
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
PATSTAT	Worldwide Patent Statistical Database
R&D	Research and Development
RISIS	Research Infrastructure for Science and Innovation Studies
SGC	Societal Grand Challenges
UFSD	University of Sheffield
UL	University of Leiden
UMAN	University of Manchester
UPEM	University of Paris Est Marne La Vallée
WoS	Web of Science
WoS	Web of Science
ZSI	Center for Social Innovation, Vienna

1 Explanation of the work carried out by the beneficiaries and Overview of the progress

The Knowledge in the Making (KNOWMAK) project has developed an interactive tool that allows selected groups of users to visualise and analyse the production of knowledge in the European Research Area, with a particular focus on knowledge related to Societal Grand Challenges (SGC²) and Key Enabling Technologies (KET³). The tool is freely available on a public website (www.knowmak.eu).

The tool is based on three existing data sources on knowledge production in the European Research Area (ERA)⁴, i.e. scientific publications derived from the Web of Science database (CWTS publication database), patents derived from PATSTAT (RISIS patent database) and European projects derived from CORDIS (RISIS-EUPRO database). Additionally, the tool includes information from the experimental database on European social innovation projects (ESID), as well as information on user attention to scholarly publications derived from twitter.

The tool has been developed through a co-creation approach that involved a group of lead users early on in the project. The group of lead users is understood as a core group of individuals who are archetypical for potential end users in terms of their data/information need, their professional experience, and their affiliation to one of the target groups, i.e. policy-makers, research managers/funders, companies, regional actors, or civil society representatives.

The KNOWMAK project lasted 36 months from January 2017 to December 2019; a preliminary version of the tool was launched in September 2018 at the STI 2018 conference in Leiden, while the final version of the tool was delivered in December 2019. As explained below in section 2, the KNOWMAK tool will be further maintained and developed within the RISIS2 Horizon2020 infrastructure project (<https://www.risis2.eu/>).

This report covers the period from M25 (January 2019) to M36 (December 2019), which corresponds to the refinement and finalization phases of the tool. The focus in this phase was in extending the tool in terms of data sources and of functionalities, improving the quality of the annotation with the ontology and refining the visual interface based on the users' feedback. The report also presents the overall achievements during the whole project.

² <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/societal-challenges>

³ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/area/key-enabling-technologies>

⁴ KNOWMAK covers EU-27 countries, EEA/EFTA countries (Iceland, Lichtenstein, Norway and Switzerland), candidate and potential candidate countries (Albania, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Kosovo, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Serbia and Turkey) and the UK.

HIGHLIGHTS: KEY ACHIEVEMENTS OF THE KNOWMAK PROJECT

- The full version of the tool is now on-line at <https://www.knowmak.eu/>. As compared with the pilot, this version provides substantially enhanced features to users including composite indicators, social innovation, country and regional factsheets, as well as actors' information.
- The final version of the ontology for Key Enabling Technologies and Societal Grand Challenges is operational and allowed producing fine-grained indicators at the topical level.
- The three 'classical' data sources (WoS scientific publications, EU-FP projects and patents), as well as social innovation projects, have been consistently tagged with the ontology and geocoded, allowing the production of regional and topic-level indicators.
- The harmonization of public-sector actors and of large firms in the three 'classical data sources has been completed and is integrated in the tool through the factsheets.
- Social innovation projects from the European Social Innovation Database (ESID) are now available in the tool.
- The tool provides additional indicators on user attention (from tweets of scientific publications) and open access to scientific publications.
- The tool has been actively disseminated through conferences, seminars and training courses, as well as through the newsletter and by producing data stories. First impacts of the tool are emerging on the intelligence of knowledge production in Europe are emerging.

The KNOWMAK consortium

The KNOWMAK consortium was originally composed by seven partners. The University of Strathclyde joined the consortium as of 01.07.2018 given the move of WP4 leader. While all partners were involved in the joint development of the tool, their tasks were specialised based on the competences and data they own. Table 1 below summarizes the main role of each partner.

Table 1. The KNOWMAK partners and their role

Partner	Lead WP	Main roles in the project
University of Paris Est Marne la Vallée (UPEM)	WP1 WP5	Project coordination. Design of the indicators. Patent data. Firms register and data.
Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT)	WP6 WP8	Development of the technical infrastructure. Data on European projects. Coordination of dissemination activities.
University of Leiden (UL)	WP3	Harmonization of actors. Data sources enhancement. Publication data. User attention data.
Politecnico of Milan (POLIMI)	-	Design of the indicators. Regional data. Dissemination activities (training).
University of Manchester (UMAN)		Social innovation actors and projects.
Zentrum für Soziale Innovation (ZSI)	WP7	User engagement and usage scenarios. Development of the user interface.
University of Sheffield (USFD)	WP2	Development of the ontologies. Annotation of data sources.
University of Strathclyde (STRATH)	WP4	Social innovation actors and projects.

1.1 Objectives and key results

The goal of the KNOWMAK project was to develop a web-based tool, which provides interactive visualisations and indicators on knowledge co-creation in the European Research Area. The tool is structured around three integrative elements:

- Research topics, as related to Societal Grand Challenges (SGC) and Key Enabling Technologies (KET; see section 1.1.4).
- Research actors, both public and private (see section 1.1.6).
- Geographical spaces and, more specifically, countries and regions, based on an adapted NUTS3 level classification (see section 1.1.5).

To this aim, the tool combines five data sources:

- Three established data sources that were already available within the consortium i.e. scientific publications, patents and European projects. These data sources were enhanced in order to be integrated in the tool.
- Two new data sources, i.e. social innovation projects derived from the Internet and citizens' attention based on twitter accounts that were developed specifically for the KNOWMAK project.

The overall process flow starting from the primary data sources to the online tool for end users is depicted in Figure 1.

In the following sections, we present the KNOWMAK tool and user interface and the underlying infrastructure.

Figure 1. The KNOWMAK overall process flow

➔ The KNOWMAK deliverable *D5.4 KNOWMAK manual* provides a high-level description of the KNOWMAK architecture and definition of indicators.

1.1.1 An overview of the KNOWMAK tool

The KNOWMAK tool is the main output of the project. It was released in September 2018 in a first version with limited functionalities and was subsequently refined and extended until the end of the project.

→ The KNOWMAK tool is publicly available at www.knowmak.eu.

For a description of the design principles of the tool the reader should refer to the KNOWMAK deliverable *D7.5 Full website and visualization environment*. The design of the tool is also extensively grounded in the elicitation of user needs presented in the KNOWMAK deliverable *D7.1. Report on user engagement and the user scenarios*.

The KNOWMAK tool consists of the landing page (see Figure 2) that contains mainly the data stories (see Figure 3) and some key information, as well as a direct link to the dashboard, i.e. the actual tool (see Figure 4). The landing page also includes a link to the project website that provides descriptive information on the KNOWMAK project (<https://project.knowmak.eu>).

Figure 2. Landing page of the tool

The data stories are meant to illustrate the value of the data that are provided by the tool for the analysis of knowledge production in Europe. They focus on the relevant insights on knowledge production that can be gained by using the tool; each story also includes ~~and~~ explanations on how to reproduce the analysis.

During the second part of the project, six stories have been published dealing with the following topics:

- Science and technology intensity: a cross-country, cross-region comparison (December 2019).

- Disseminating scientific knowledge: open access and social media (November 2019).
- Specialising in industrial biotechnology? A perspective on countries (March 2019)
- Knowledge production trends in nanoscience and technology (December 2018)
- The private-public divide in genomics research (August 2018)
- Small regions: big players in knowledge production (August 2018)

Stories have also been widely disseminated through the KNOWMAK newsletter (see section 2).

Figure 3. Example of data story

17 December 2019

Science and technology intensity: a cross-country, cross-region comparison

Our analysis confirms that few locations in Europe are responsible for most of the knowledge production. Germany is by far the most relevant country in terms of technology intensity. However, science and technology do not follow the same agglomeration patterns. RISIS-KNOWMAK reveals which small regions show a relatively high intensity of both technological and scientific knowledge production, even higher than the largest metropolitan areas.

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The RISIS-KNOWMAK tool provides two composite indicators that offer a synthetic view on science and technology intensity of European countries and regions. These indicators enable to address relevant questions, such as do we observe differences in the production of technological knowledge across European countries? Does scientific knowledge production follow the same diffusion patterns? Are small regions relevant in this respect, compared to large metropolitan regions? Do we observe spatial agglomeration patterns and, if so, are these the same for science and for technology?

These questions can be addressed directly in the RISIS-KNOWMAK tool with the new composite indicators. First, Figures 1 and 2 show the technology share intensity and the science share intensity indicators, respectively, by country in 2013 for the largest European countries in terms of population (Germany, France, UK, Italy, Spain, and Poland). For both indicators, values greater (lower) than 1 mean that the intensity of (technological or scientific) knowledge production of a country is higher (lower) than the European average. Germany has by far the highest score in technology intensity (technology share intensity = 3.1), followed by France (1.2). The other countries lag behind with values lower than 1. The production of scientific knowledge is spread more evenly, with UK having the highest score (science share intensity = 1.2), while France and Germany are in line with the European average.

Although the analysis on the regional level confirms the above findings overall, it also reveals some interesting spatial patterns (see Figures 3 and 4). First, most of the regions which exhibit the highest values of technology share intensity are located in Southern Germany, like Regensburg and Mannheim-Ludwigshafen. Notable exceptions are Jena in the Central area of Germany, Grenoble in France, and Cambridgeshire in the UK. Second, when looking at the science share intensity indicator, UK regions like Southampton, Cambridgeshire, and Oxfordshire score highest. Interestingly, among the most important scientific hubs are Italian regions such as Trieste and Pisa. Third, for both indicators the largest metropolitan areas, such as London and Paris, do have very high scores.

Figure 5 compares the technology share intensity (vertical axis) and the science share intensity (horizontal axis) by region. Overall, we observe substantial variation in both indicators and in their relationships. Jena ranks #1 for technology intensity and #2 for science intensity. Heidelberg and Cambridgeshire exhibit high values for both indicators, but follow at distance. The German regions of Regensburg and Mannheim-Ludwigshafen exhibit a high performance in terms of technology intensity, but a lower one in terms of science intensity. The opposite can be observed for university-based regions such as Oxfordshire, Trieste, or Pisa. We did not register any regions from Poland or Spain among the most intensive regions.

Figure 1: Technology share intensity by country

Methodology ▼

Additional Resources ▼

1.1.2 The dashboard

The KNOWMAK tool itself (dashboard) follows a logic that resembles sentences of the human language (English), e.g. *explore the number of publications by country in 2014*. This way it is clear to the users what the key objective of the present search is. The logic behind this and its key elements are described in the following (see Figure 4)

Figure 4: KNOWMAK Tool - dashboard

The tool provides a number of important functions to users:

- The selection of indicators. Indicator examples are the number of publications, or the number of patents, or the number of EU-FP participations (1 in the figure).
- The selection of the exploration mode in terms of geography (country or region and/or topics, at the KET/SGC level and at the level of subclasses (135 subareas of KET and SGC; 2 and 3 in the figure).
- The year of reference. Data are provided for the years 2000-2016 (2000-2013 for patents; 4 in the figure).

Based on these choices, it is possible to produce maps of countries and regions of Europe of knowledge production either aggregated or for individual topics or subtopics. Switching to the table views, it is further possible to download the data for further analysis. For some choices, the tool also offers a bar chart view in order to analyse the distribution across regions and/or topics (5 in the figure; see also Figure 5). Finally, for each country or region, a summary factsheet can be opened providing basic indicators, identifying the top actors in knowledge production and selected social innovation projects. Importantly, the factsheet is topic and year

dependent and, therefore, allows for a fine-grained analysis of regional specialisation.

Figure 5. Example of bar chart view

→ For a detailed presentation of the tool functionalities, the reader should refer to the KNOWMAK deliverable *D6.5 User handbook* available on the tool through the help function.

1.1.3 Indicators

The KNOWMAK tool is an indicator tool: users do not access micro-level data, for example individual publications, but will be provided different types of indicators relative to combinations of the three integrative dimensions, i.e. space, topics and actors.

Indicators are meant to provide synthetic information to users in a condensed form, therefore avoiding too complex visualization or large amount of data to be examined. Indicators need to be grounded on specific user questions and theoretical representation of the considered phenomena. On the other hand, indicators are also grounded on statistical analysis of the available data, which might highlight regularities and, for example, correlations between variables.

The basic choice in KNOWMAK has been to rely on rather simple indicators, mostly counts of research output, while focusing on their fine-grained disaggregation by geographical spaces (39 countries and 575 regions) and by topic (13 classes and 135 subclasses).

→ The KNOWMAK deliverable *D5.4 KNOWMAK manual* provides a detailed methodological description of the indicators as available in the tool.

The tool currently provides three types of basic count indicators, for scientific production and outreach (five indicators), technological production (two indicators) and European research projects (two indicators). All of them are available by geographical space (country or region) and by topics (class or subclass), both in absolute values and normalised by the number of inhabitants (see Table 2). Additionally, four composite indicators have been developed to characterize the knowledge production for each geographical space and topic in terms of share of the whole ERA knowledge production, of the intensity as compared with ERA average and of the orientation towards science vs. technology. These allow a fine-grained analysis of the structure of knowledge production at the regional level (see box below). Finally, three network-centrality indicator are provided that allow analysing the network centrality of countries and regions by dimension and topic. All indicators can be downloaded in .csv format for further analysis by users through a dedicated download interface.

Table 2. List of available indicators in the tool

Category	Indicator	Data source	Type
Scientific production and outreach	Number of publications	CWTS publication database	Count
	Number of publications in the Top10% cited		Count
	Number of international scientific collaborations		Count
	Number of publications tweeted		Count
	Number of publications Open Access		Count
Technological production	Number of patent applications	RISIS patent database	Count
	Number of transnational patent applications		Count

European research projects	Number of EU-FP participations	RISIS-EUPRO	Count
	Number of EU-FP coordination	RISIS-EUPRO	Count
Composite indicators	Knowledge production share	CWTS publication database, RISIS patent database, RISIS-EUPRO	Scale
	Knowledge production intensity		Scale
	Technology share intensity		Scale
	Science share intensity		Scale
Country/regional data	Number of inhabitants	EUROSTAT	Scale
Network centrality indicators	Publication degree centrality	CWTS publication database	Scale
	Patent degree centrality	RISIS patent database	Scale
	Project degree centrality	RISIS-EUPRO	Scale

Box: analyzing the regional knowledge production through KNOWMAK indicators

In this paper, we develop an analysis of the spatial distribution of knowledge production related to Key Enabling Technologies (KETs) and Societal Grand Challenges (SGCs) in Europe building on an extensive dataset developed in the H2020 KNOWMAK project. We first provide a broad characterization of European regions in terms of their knowledge volume and knowledge intensity, which leads to a distinction between the large metropolitan regions and smaller knowledge intensive regions. Second, by using principal component analysis, we identify three components of knowledge production that we broadly characterize as academic production, technology production and educational production. This distinction allows further categorizing regions in terms of the balance between these components, which we suggest is also related to the ecology of actors in a region and, notably, of the importance of public-sector research and of knowledge producing firms. By using advanced statistical techniques, i.e. latent class analysis, a new classification of regions by the orientation of their knowledge production.

Lepori, B., P. Laredo, T. Scherngell, D. Maynard, and M. Guerini. "The spatial distribution of knowledge production in Europe. Evidence from KET and SGC." In *17th International Conference on Scientometrics and Informetrics, ISSI 2019*, vol. 2, pp. 685-690. 2019.

1.1.4 Topics: the KNOWMAK ontology

The selection of topics is based on a fine-grained ontology of KET and SGC developed within RISIS-KNOWMAK and which includes 135 classes (Data are attributed to classes through linguistic techniques, based on the frequency of keywords within documents, such as titles and abstracts of publications in the Web of Science, and deep learning based on a large collection of relevant data. This approach has proved to be very flexible in connecting topics of policy interest with heterogeneous data sources characterized by a very specific language.

Figure 6).

Data are attributed to classes through linguistic techniques, based on the frequency of keywords within documents, such as titles and abstracts of publications in the Web of Science, and deep learning based on a large collection of relevant data. This approach has proved to be very flexible in connecting topics of policy interest with heterogeneous data sources characterized by a very specific language.

Figure 6. Ontology topics in RISIS-KNOWMAK

The development of the ontology and of the associated annotation service has been a core task of the project. An ontology is essentially a hierarchical representation of topics, but with the possibility of multiple inheritance (a topic can be represented as a subclass of more than one class). On the audience side, ontologies are a means to translate questions of interest, frequently expressed in generic terms in policy documents, into a formal structure of classes and keywords. On the data side, through instances (keywords), ontologies can be connected to different and evolving vocabularies across data sources. Ontologies thus effectively work as a bridge between (policy) questions and heterogeneous data sources with their own language such publications and patents (

Figure 7).

Figure 7. The role of an ontology in connecting policy questions from users with data sources

The KNOWMAK ontology has been built around the thirteen Societal Grand Challenges (SGC⁵) and Key Enabling Technologies (KET⁶), as the core policy dimensions for the Horizon2020 programme; the approach is however flexible and can be extended in future to other policy-relevant topics, such as missions to be introduced in Horizon Europe. The thirteen SGC and KET classes have been further decomposed by relying on existing ontologies, such as nature.com, as well on the analysis of policy documents. This process had led to a final structure including 135 subclasses.

The second core step has been populating the ontology with keywords, which allow linking classes and subclasses with documents such as publications and EU-FP projects based on their textual content. This is challenging task since differences in vocabularies within academia, industry and society mean that the same concepts are typically expressed in different ways, especially in patents, which are extremely technical. Existing attempts at classification have highlighted these issues. Following a series of initial experiments, the solution adopted involves multiple layers of keyword extraction and a mixture of automated techniques interspersed with expert knowledge at key junctures. Starting from a core of high-quality keywords selected manually, different steps of automatic enrichment have been performed; a key challenge in this respect was excluding generic keywords that have multiple meanings, such as 'learning'. The current version of the ontology includes 6,790 unique keywords and 9,076 pairs of keywords per classes, i.e. an average of 46 keywords per class.

The third core step was to classify documents by attributing them to classes and subclasses based on the frequency and combination of keywords in their textual content, such as title, abstract and keywords for publications. To this aim a classifier was developed that takes documents and returns information about the class(es) to which each is linked, along with a score per class. Finally, documents are assigned to the classes for which they have a score above the median.

⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/societal-challenges>

⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/area/key-enabling-technologies>

The ontology development process went through successive iteration steps; the results were evaluated through statistical analysis of the distribution of documents by class, as well as by manual checking of some individual documents. This led to successive improvements in the ontology structure (for example reducing overlaps between some subclasses), to fine-tuning the scoring method and, more importantly, to improvements in the keyword selection processes and in the exclusion of ambiguous words. While the current results look very reasonable, a further refinement and a more systematic evaluation will be undertaken in the RISIS2 project.

Core deliverables on the ontology

→ *D2.4 Report on ontologies and tagging* provides a full description of the ontology development process, including also technical details.

→ *D2.5 Maynard D., Lepori B., Larédo Ph. (2019), Using ontologies to map between research data and policymakers' presumptions. The experience of the KNOWMAK project, Scientometrics, draft paper.* Discusses the principles in the design of the ontology by focusing on the interaction between expert judgement and natural language processing.

1.1.5 Space: the KNOWMAK regional structure

The second core integrative dimension of KNOWMAK is space, meaning that all indicators can be associated with geographical spaces, allowing therefore comparing space in terms of the volume and characteristics of their knowledge production. To this aim, all source data in KNOWMAK have been geolocalised at least at the city level based on the authors' (publications), participants' (projects), inventors' addresses (patents) and localization of key actor social innovation projects). This, in principle, would allow associating indicators to any geographical space of interest.

In KNOWMAK, spatial structure has been implemented at two levels, countries and regions. For the latter, a core innovation has been the development of a regional classification that fits the structure of knowledge production in Europe, while remaining fully compatible with the EUROSTAT NUTS regional classification⁷. This compatibility allows combining all KNOWMAK data with regional statistics (at NUTS3 level, 2016 edition) from EUROSTAT.

More precisely, the classification includes EUROSTAT metropolitan regions (based on the aggregation of NUTS3-level regions) and NUTS2 regions for the remaining areas; further, a few additional centers for knowledge production, like Oxford and Leuven, have been singled out at NUTS3 level. The resulting classification is therefore more fine-grained than NUTS2 in the areas with sizeable knowledge production, but at the same time recognizes the central role of metropolitan areas in knowledge production. While remaining compatible with NUTS, the classification allows addressing two well-known shortcomings: a) the fact that some large cities are split between NUTS regions (London) and b) the fact that NUTS3 classification in some countries includes many very small regions, as in the case of Germany.

For example, in the case of Belgium presented in

Figure 8, EUROSTAT identifies five metropolitan regions (Brussels, Gent, Antwerp, Liège and Charleroi) and singles out an additional knowledge hub at NUTS3 level (Leuven). Additionally, nine regions are created corresponding either to original NUTS2 regions (such as the province of Luxembourg) or to NUTS2 regions without the metropolitan regions (such as the province of Antwerp, which corresponds to NUTS3 subregions of the province not included in the Antwerp metropolitan regions). Overall, the original 44 NUTS3 regions have been reduced to 15 regions by grouping together small rural areas without a significant knowledge production. For the whole of ERA, the adapted classification includes 573 regions, as compared with 1522 NUTS3 regions in EUROSTAT (2016 edition).

⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/background>.

Figure 8. KNOWMAK regional classification. The example of Belgium

→ The KNOWMAK regional structure is described in more detail in the deliverable *D5.4 KNOWMAK manual*.

1.1.6 Actors: public and private research organizations

Research organizations in the public sector (Higher Education Institutions, Public Research Organizations) and in the private sector (R&D laboratories of firms) are a core component of knowledge production; it can be argued that the volume, quality and composition of knowledge production is closely associated with the ecology of research organizations present in a geographical space, for example a region. Therefore, for the purposes of KNOWMAK, it is highly relevant to be able to identify the most important actors in knowledge production specific to the type of knowledge produced and to the topic of interest. This might also serve a second purpose of the KNOWMAK tool, i.e. to allow the identification of research partners in specific domains.

To this aim, KNOWMAK builds on extensive standardization of research organizations performed through two core RISIS facilities, i.e. the register of public research organizations OrgReg (available on-line at orgreg.joanneum.at) and the register of firms engaged in knowledge production FirmReg (currently available as internal service).

The Register of European public-sector research organizations (OrgReg) is a new facility developed within the RISIS project. Orgreg includes all public-sector research organizations with a sizeable research or tertiary education output, broadly corresponding to the sum of the Higher Education, Government and Private Non-Profit sector as defined in the Frascati manual. For each organization, OrgReg provides unique and stable identifiers, basic descriptive information, geographical information, as well as information on organizational linkages and organizational demography. It currently includes over 6,000 public research organizations in the same countries covered by KNOWMAK.

The firms register (FirmReg) is a central facility within RISIS which aims at uniquely identifying and tracking over time all the businesses included in the firms datasets which are part of RISIS, and allowing the addition of more firms datasets over time. It is built around the same principles as OrgReg and will be hosted on the same technical platform. In future, it will be extended to all firms with a sizeable knowledge production, as measured by their scientific and technological output.

→ KNOWMAK deliverable *D5.3 Actors' harmonization* provides a detailed description of the actors' harmonization process in KNOWMAK, while the following paper (also available as KNOWMAK deliverable D3.3 describes the conceptual roots of OrgReg:

→ Lepori B. (2020), A register of public-sector research organizations as a tool for research policy studies and evaluation, Research Evaluation, forthcoming.

To embed OrgReg and FirmReg within KNOWMAK, the respective organizational identifiers have been introduced in the three main source databases, i.e. CWTS publication database, RISIS patent database and RISIS-EUPRO for European projects. This process has been completed for public organizations and, as of firms, for the largest knowledge production firms included in the RISIS Corporate Invention and Innovation Boards (RISIS-CIB). This allows computing within

KNOWMAK indicators on counts of publications, patents and projects for individual research organizations in a topic and a given geographical space.

For the KNOWMAK tool, this infrastructure allows displaying for each topic and for individual countries and regions, the list of the five public and private actors with the largest number of publications, patents⁸ and European projects. Basic information on these organizations, such as the location of the headquarters and the website, can also be retrieved thanks to the interconnection with OrgReg and FirmReg.

We notice that the assignment is not based on the organizational address, but on the location specified in each output (such as the address provided in a scientific publication). This allows correctly locating outputs of multi-site institutions; for example, CNRS is correctly shown as one of the main publishing actors in the Grenoble region, despite its headquarters being situated in Paris.

In this respect, the main added value of the organizational module in KNOWMAK is its connection with the ontology; while the main research actors by country and region in the aggregate are rather easy to identify, KNOWMAK allows to single out the most important actors by topic, a fine-grained information, which is not available elsewhere. Preliminary investigations of these data show important (and expected) differences in the top-actors list by topics, for example between KET and SGCs.

The actors' module will be further extended within the RISIS2 project in two directions: completing the coverage of private actors with small and medium size firms and provide direct access to organizational-level indicators through OrgReg and FirmReg.

⁸ For patents, the identification of top-private actors will be completed in spring 2020 within the RISIS2 project.

1.1.7 Beyond classical knowledge production: social innovation and user attention

A limitation of many available indicators in S&T is that they are focused on the knowledge being codified and recognized by the scientific community. While they are relevant to map the existing science and technology basis, most users require on-time indicators on emergent topics and actors (*knowledge in the making*). Furthermore, a focus on knowledge developed within structured R&D contexts does not allow for the tracking of broader processes of social innovation, constituting a core dimension of the new modes of knowledge co-creation.

Therefore, an important objective of KNOWMAK was to provide some indicators covering non-conventional knowledge production activities, as well as capturing also the broader societal outreach of knowledge production. Since such indicators are less established than conventional ones such as publications and patents, activities and results in this respect have a more experimental character and will be further developed within RISIS2.

More specifically, KNOWMAK has implemented two experiments in this direction.

a) The development and integration of a database of European social innovation, broadly defined as innovations that satisfy societal needs including the needs of particular social groups and are primarily created by social actors such as non-governmental organizations or grassroots movements. To this aim, KNOWMAK has developed the European Social Innovation Database (ESID), constituted through the crawling and coding (largely through advanced machine learning approaches) of various data sources and databases on social innovation. The current release of ESID contains over 9,500 distinct social innovation projects; for 2,600 projects, the relevant data have been completed and checked systematically. These projects have also been annotated with the ontology and geolocalised in order to be integrated in the KNOWMAK database. To this extent, the ontology has also been extended to include additional subclasses associated with social innovation, such as 'housing', 'local engagement' and 'migration'.

→ The approach to social innovation and the ESID database are described in *D4.4 Report on social innovation indicators and the ESID database*.

Among these, 1,749 projects, located in the ERA and fulfilling the inclusion criteria, are currently displayed in KNOWMAK. For each selection of geographical space and topics, a list of social innovation projects can be visualized in the factsheet and basic information on the project (title, location, abstract, website) can be retrieved (see

Figure 9). This allows users to look for good examples of social innovation in specific subject domains and geographical spaces.

Figure 9. Social innovation projects in RISIS-KNOWMAK

The screenshot shows the RISIS-KNOWMAK interface. At the top, there are buttons for 'Show', 'CLASS', and 'SOCIETY'. To the right, there are view options: 'MAP', 'BAR', and 'TABLE'. The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column shows a list of projects under the heading 'PARIS France'. The selected project is 'Auto-entrepreneurs: starting a project with confidence'. The right column displays the details for this project, including a description, website, location, topics, and project start date.

Auto-entrepreneurs: starting a project with confidence	
The Entrepreneurs de la Cité Foundation assures disadvantaged entrepreneurs, thus facilitating their reintegration into the economic and social sphere.	
Website	http://www.fondationcaritasfrance.org/projets-soutenus/auto-...
Location	Paris, France
Topics	Entrepreneurship, Housing, Social inequality, Society
Project start	2006

b) Two indicators on social outreach of scientific publications, derived from the CWTS publication database, are included in the KNOWMAK tool.

The first indicator is the count of publications that are tweeted in the social media platform Twitter (via links in tweets to scientific publications). The data used includes publications published after 2011 that have been tweeted at least once, derived from data provided by Altmetric (<https://www.altmetric.com/>) and stored in the CWTS publication database. Choosing tweeted publications as an (altmetric) indicator takes into account that Twitter is among the most prominent sources regarding the dissemination of scientific publications. Furthermore, the dissemination of publications on Twitter can be considered to indicate the exposure to (and interest in) scientific output not only among academics, but also among other social media users from the general public.

The second indicator is the number and share of publications that are either published on open access journals or are available on a public repository, as an indicator of the broader availability of scientific publication beyond the scholarly audience⁹.

By combining these indicators with topics and geographical spaces, it becomes therefore possible to analyze variations in the extent of user attention and open access by country and by topic to understand how these are related to different

⁹ <https://www.cwts.nl/blog?article=n-r2w2a4&title=indicators-of-open-access-publishing-in-the-cwts-leiden-ranking-2019>

characteristics of scientific domains, but also to institutional cultures across Europe (see Figure 10).

Figure 10. Percentage of open access (vertical axis) and tweeted (horizontal axis) publications by country

→ User attention and open access indicators are described in *D4.3 Indicators of Twitter presence and Open Access publication, and identification of influential users of research on Twitter*.

1.1.8 Behind the scene: the KNOWMAK technical infrastructure

The KNOWMAK data infrastructure constitutes the main linking mechanism between “input” and “output” oriented activities in KNOWMAK. It is intended to ensure a smooth and efficient data flow, beginning from the source datasets hosted by different partners and characterised by different technical choices, to the final indicators being conveyed to the users of the web tool in form of data extracts, tables and visualisations.

The overall architecture of the KNOWMAK infrastructure consists of three main components that dynamically interact with each other in terms of data production, data handling, data storage, indicators calculation and data visualisation. Figure 11 provides an illustration of these components of the KNOWMAK data infrastructure, namely the primary datasets, the KNOWMAK central database and the KNOWMAK web-based tool.

Figure 11. The KNOWMAK data infrastructure

The first essential building block of the KNOWMAK infrastructure are the three databases containing the enriched data, i.e. the Web of Science version at the University of Leiden, the EUPRO database of EU-FP projects at AIT and the RISIS patent database at IFRIS, as well as the European Social Innovation Database developed by WP5.

The enriched data are transferred from the partners hosting the source datasets to the KNOWMAK central database (hosted by AIT). It constitutes the central linking mechanism between the source data and the web tool, and is developed in a way to ensure flexibility and efficiency in indicators production at the same time.

The KNOWMAK central database has been designed in order to store all required information to produce the indicators, but to avoid transferring unnecessary information that would increase the amount of data, particularly textual descriptions. To this aim, a standard data transfer format for each data source has been defined. The database comprises two layers: the central database (efficiently storing all data necessary for indicators) and the indicators layer pre-calculating indicators to efficiently transfer them to the tool.

Figure 12 illustrates the condensed data structure of the KNOWMAK central database, which has only slightly changed from the first release. The boxes in blue color articulate the necessary information to be extracted from the source datasets and to be transferred to the KNOWMAK central database across three main dimensions that are actors, actor sites and activities. To integrate aggregated information in terms of indicator production, the respective tables on actors, actor sites and activities are linked with our integrative dimensions that are key actors, geographical spaces (country and regions) and topical classes.

Figure 12. Basic structure of the KNOWMAK central database

Notes: Integrative elements are given in the orange boxes, integrated information from source datasets in the blue boxes; behind the boxes lays a series of inter-related tables designed to effectively extract indicators (including some junction tables not displayed here);

The indicators layer is generated from the KNOWMAK central database. It serves to rapidly provide indicator values to users of the KNOWMAK web tool, while containing no information unavailable to the KNOWMAK central database—it is an essential optimization for a usable tool.

Next to the definition of an appropriate indicators layer of the KNOWMAK central database, another element is particularly important in terms of efficiency, i.e. the Application Programming Interface (API) pushing the indicators on-the-fly to the web tool. To this aim, an intermediate software has been developed that allows the KNOWMAK central database and the web tool to communicate with each other by means of a REST (Representational State Transfer) API. Distinct main endpoints are used for the distinct knowledge types (so far publications, projects and

patents), where the indicators for each of them can be specified. Depending on the knowledge type and the indicator chosen, limitations by actor, by geographical territory and by topic can be made. The communication consists of API calls or requests using these endpoints. All data operations in the KNOWMAK web tool can be accessed via API calls following the RESTful architectural style.

→ A detailed presentation of the data infrastructure is provided in the KNOWMAK deliverable *D6.1 Report on the design of the infrastructure* and in the KNOWMAK deliverable *D6.4 Final release of the database*.

1.2 Explanation of the work carried per WP

1.2.1 Work Package 1

WP leader: UPEM

WP objectives: WP1 implements management procedures that secure the scientific and technical dimension of the project's implementation, manage internal communication and decision-making, oversee the activities of the work packages and the respect of timing and deliverables and manage the communication with the European Commission.

Tasks and activities

Task 1.1. Communication and reporting to the European Commission

In order to ensure a good communication and handling pending issues, the scientific coordinator had regular phone calls with the Scientific Officer (SO) at the EC. Additionally, the SO has participated to the project kick-off meeting 9-10.01.2017.

This task also involved the preparation of the following documents:

- 1st periodic technical report at M12 (31.12.2017).
- 1st financial report at M12 (31.12.2017).
- D1.3 Interim report at M24 (31.12.2018).
- 2nd period technical report at M36 (31.12.2019).

Finally, the coordinator has coordinated the preparation of the project review by the European Commission that took place 01.03.2018 in Brussels and the documentation need for the additional distance review in November 2018.

Task 1.2. Monitoring the functioning of WP activities and partners' responsibilities

Monitoring and coordination of the WP activities has been performed through the following measures:

- Three plenary project meetings devoted to the overall coordination of the project work and, particularly, to the integration between WPs. They have taken place in Paris (10-11.01.2017), in Milan (22-23.11.2017) and in Sheffield (23-24.10.2018). All partners have participated.
- Ad hoc technical meetings devoted to coordination of specific activities (21.06.2017, 12.09.2017, 02.03.2018, 26.03.2018, 22.08.2018, 13.12.2018; 20.03.2019; 19.09.2019).
- Regular skype meetings devoted to the overall coordination of the project and to specific issues.
- Frequent skype communication between the coordinator and groups of partners to deal with specific issues, more particularly the design of the infrastructure and the development and implementation of the ontology.
- Regular skype exchanges between the coordinator and the partners for managing activities and preparing deliverables.
- Review by the coordinator of the individual deliverables to ensure quality – some being subject to extensive revisions.

Task 1.3 Data Management Plan

The draft Data Management Plan has been submitted at M6; based also on the feedback from the European Commission it has been revised and submitted as final document at M18. The integration of the KNOWMAK tool in RISIS has some implications for data management that are further discussed in section 0 of this report.

Short description of deliverables

D1.1: Draft Data Management Plan

D1.2: Final Data Management Plan. This deliverable describes the data management policy of the project and further steps needed to implement it.

D1.3: Interim progress report. This report presents the advancement of the project in the first 24 months, the criticalities and deviations from the original plan and the roadmap for the third project year.

Milestones

MS1. Project successfully started (M3). Status: achieved.

1.2.2 Work package 2. Ontology creation and data annotation

WP leader: USFD

WP objectives: To derive from policy documents and project descriptions two ontologies referring respectively to Societal Grand Challenges and to key enabling technologies. To develop methods for tagging the data items in WP3 with the ontologies.

Tasks and activities

Task 2.1 Constitution of two seed document corpora

A first seed document corpus was constituted until M4 including policy documents and FP workprogramme descriptions (136 documents); the ontology was also built on the IPC classes vocabulary and on the CORDIS project database. An extension of this corpus has taken place in spring 2018 by specifically tailoring areas where the keywords for the ontology are not sufficient for high-quality text annotation. This includes some additional policy documents, but also other sources relevant for the generation of the ontology and, specifically, textual content from publications, projects and patents.

Task 2.2 Methodology for ontology creation and semi-automatic tagging

The ontology has been released and stabilised and extensively populated with keywords (over 2,400 keywords); the annotation service is also operational through the GATE service and has been successively updated with the new version of the ontology.

Task 2.3 Ontologies extension and tagging methodologies for all sources

From M6, the ontology has been revised constantly by adding new keywords, adding stopwords and refining the annotation process in close interaction with the data source owners. This process was continued until the final release of the ontology, which has taken place in August 2019.

Description of deliverables

D2.1. Database of key documents. This deliverable provides 110 policy documents for the ontology as the main outcome of T2.1.

D2.2. Report on ontologies and tagging. This deliverable provides a full description of the ontology design and enrichment process, as well as of data source annotation.

D2.3. Extended database of key documents. Extended version of D2.1 including also documents on missions, as well as other textual sources.

D2.4 Report on ontologies and tagging, extended. This report fully documents the further refinement and extension of the ontology until end of the project.

D2.5. Scientific paper on the set up of ontologies (M12). This paper has been presented at the Science, Technology and Innovation conference 2019 in Rome and is currently under consideration for publication at Scientometrics. It presents the guiding principles of the KNOWMAK ontology development and, particularly, focuses on the interaction between expert assessment and natural language processing techniques.

Milestones

MS3. First release of ontologies and tagging. Status: achieved.

MS4. Final release of ontologies and tagging. Status: achieved.

1.2.3 Work package 3. Data sources treatment and enhancement

WP leader: UL

WP objectives: To extend and enhance the databases on publications, patents and projects by:

- Tagging all data items through the use of ontologies developed in WP2.
- Harmonization of the actors' names linked to the KNOWMAK master actors' list.
- Extending the EUPRO database to the most important European transnational programs.

Tasks and activities.

Task 3.1. Publication database

The CWTS publication database in Leiden is being updated regularly based on new releases of the Web of Science (WoS); actors' standardization is largely complete for public organizations and for the largest firms performing R&D.

The dataset has been annotated with the final version of the ontology for the years 2000-2016 and fully geocoded at the city level.

Task 3.2 RISIS patent database

The update to the PATSTAT version 2016 and the corresponding enhancements have been concluded in spring 2018. The database has been geocoded and annotated with the ontology; the standardization process of public actors has also been concluded, while firms will be standardized in spring 2020 within the RISIS2 project.

Task 3.3 Extension of the European projects database

Enhancement of the EUPRO database with geographical coordinates and public-sector actors is concluded and been performed for large firms. The whole database has been annotated with the ontology.

Short description of deliverables

D3.1 Report on databases enhancement and tagging. This report describes the steps, status and results of the database enhancement, i.e. standardization of actors, geolocation and annotation with the ontology.

D3.2 Report on databases enhancement and tagging, extended. This report documents the final status of the database enhancement within WP3, as of the end of the project.

D3.3 Scientific paper on harmonization. This paper, which will be published in the journal Research Evaluation, describes in detail the principles and implementation of the actors' harmonization within KNOWMAK and the related RISIS2 project.

Milestones

MS5. First release of tagged databases (M12). Status: achieved.

MS6. Second release of tagged databases (M24). Status: achieved.

MS7. Final release of tagged databases. Status: achieved.

1.2.4 Work package 4. Social Innovation and user attention

WP leader: UMAN (later University of Strathclyde)

WP objectives: This work package will extend the project sources to non-conventional users in knowledge production, the identification of social innovation projects and the measure of user attention to knowledge topics.

Tasks and activities.

Task 4.1. Identification of social innovation projects and non-conventional actors

A methodological manual has been released providing definitions of social innovation, criteria for the identification of projects and actors and a list of variables to be collected. Based on the manual, the social innovation projects database (ESID) has been designed and is being populated by crawling sources available on the Internet (about 4,000 projects and actors estimated). Tests for collecting data combining manual annotation and machine learning techniques have been completed.

Task 4.2 Characterizing social innovation projects and non-conventional actors

The identified social innovation projects have been characterized as of their content, annotated with the ontology and geolocalised. The dataset has been delivered to the central KNOWMAK database and integrated in the KWOWMAK tool. Given the limited number of project, we renounced to a characterization of the actors. The full database contains in total over 9,500 projects, of which 1,749 fulfil the criteria and are displayed in the KNOWMAK tool.

Task 4.3 Identification of influential users of research through social media

Data on user attention based on twitter have been cleaned and linked to the Web of Science database at CWTS; institutional accounts are also being linked to academic organizations and the standardization of influential users is on-going. The corresponding indicators are now integrated in the KNOWMAK tool; additionally, this task has been extended to the provision of indicators on open access publications from the CWTS database.

Short description of deliverables

D4.1 Report on social innovation projects. This report presents the design, methods and sources of the ESID database. It provides also some statistical information on the current content of the database and the steps planned for its integration in the KNOWMAK tool.

D4.2. Database of social innovation projects. This report describes the structure and content of the ESID database, as well as the data integrated in the KNOWMAK tool.

D4.3 Influential users database and report. This report presents the methods for the analysis of twitter accounts and of open access publications and describes the integration of the corresponding indicators in the KNOWMAK tool.

D4.4. Final database of social innovation projects. To be added

Milestones.

MS8. Database of social innovation projects. Status: achieved.

MS9. Delivery of influential users' database. Status: achieved.

1.2.5 Work package 5. Integrative methodologies and tools

WP leader: UPEM.

WP objectives: The objective of this WP is to develop three core elements needed to integrate the data items collected in WP3 and WP4, complementing the ontologies developed in WP2:

- To develop and maintain a harmonized list of actors identified in WP3 and WP4 data sources.
- To define indicators and data scores to be computed from the data items and visualized in WP5.
- To provide an infrastructure for the spatial representation of knowledge co-creation.

Tasks and activities

5.1 Harmonized list and actors' characterization

This task has involved the completion of the OrgReg RISIS facility and its integration within KNOWMAK. The actors' list for the public sector is now available in the tool. Integration of the actors' lists for firms has been completed for large R&D performing firms and is now integrated in the tool; for patents, this step will be finalized in spring 2020 through the RISIS2 project.

5.2 Definition of indicators and of data scores

This task involved extensive work in integrating the elements of the tool in a consistent design and was therefore critical for the whole project. It also involved extensive work with the partners to select a core set of indicators and decide at which aggregation level to implement them and how to compute indicators. The final list of indicators is now available in the tool.

5.3 Actors' and data items geolocalisation & clustering

This task involved two activities. First, a suitable regional level was defined by aggregating EUROSTAT NUTS3 at the level of metropolitan regions; regional statistics for this classification has also been integrated in the database. Second, a geocoding service has been established; city-level geocoding is now available for the vast majority of data items and is integrated in the tool.

Short description of deliverables

D5.1 Report on actors' harmonization, draft. This report describes the strategy for actors' harmonization and provides details on how the RISIS facilities Orgreg and FirmReg will be integrated in the KNOWMAK tool.

D5.2 KNOWMAK manual This report provides a consistent description of the overall design of the KNOWMAK tool by integrating all workpackages and elements. It also includes the list of indicators and how they have been operationalized for different levels of aggregation (specifically actors, space and topics). The manual therefore represents a key integrative element for the whole project.

D5.3 Report on actors' harmonization, final. This report presents the final status of the actors' harmonization process within KNOWMAK, by extending and updating D5.3.

D5.4 KNOWMAK manual final. This is the final version D5.2 presenting the overall architecture of the tool and the final list of indicators.

Milestones

MS11. First actors' list available. Status: achieved.

MS12. First indicators list available. Status: achieved.

MS13. Geolocalisation for three sources. Status: achieved.

MS14. Final actors' list available. Status: achieved.

MS15. Final indicators list available. Status: achieved.

1.2.6 Work package 6. Data Management System

WP leader: AIT.

WP objectives: WP6 is concerned with specifying a data representation that maintains the data integrity and that supports the implementation of an interface that satisfies user needs. To fill these requirements, WP6 will include an initial specification of a relational database management system; implementation of a pilot database with basic facilities; and iterative development of a full database.

Tasks and activities

6.1 Definition of the data model and pilot database

The development of the data model was started in March 2017 in close interaction with WP5. A first prototype was set-up in June 2017 populated with a limited set of data to test the suitability of the data model. Based on the pilot's experience, the data model has been finalized and the database has been implemented until M18 as the underlying infrastructure for the data tool.

6.2 Data extraction and indicators building

The indicators layer of the database and the procedures for the indicators' building and transfer via API to the tool are now fully operational.

6.3 Full database and data management procedures

This task involves the maintenance and further development of the data management system after the first release of the tool. It has been completed with the final release at the end of 2019.

6.4 The KNOWMAK handbook

The KNOWMAK handbook provides a full description of the tool and of the indicators available tailored specifically to users. It is has been subsequently updated to the final version of the tool.

Short description of deliverables

D6.1 Report on the data structure. Status: delivered. This report describes the KNOWMAK data structure and the technical choices made to implement it. It has represented the reference for the implementation of the Data Management System.

D6.2 First release of the database. Status: delivered. The database is now fully operational; the accompanying document describes shortly its architecture and technical implementation.

D6.3. Full release of the database. Status: delivered. This report accompanies the full release of the KNOWMAK database in September 2019.

D6.4. Final release of the database. Status: delivered. This report accompanies the full release of the KNOWMAK database in December 2019.

D6.5 KNOWMAK handbook draft. Status: delivered.

D6.6 Final KNOWMAK handbook. Status: delivered

Milestones

MS17. First release of the database (M18). Status: achieved.

1.2.7 Work package 7. User interaction and visualization

WP leader: ZSI.

WP objectives:

- Define how users can access the evidence on European knowledge production and co-creation that is collected through KNOWMAK's data management and analysis processes.
- Engaging users in the design of the KNOWMAK platform to ensure usability, usage and sustainability.
- Offering customisable visualisations of European knowledge production and co-creation.
- Help to support evidence-based policymaking, research investment decision-making and co-creation.

Tasks and activities

7.1 Web environment

Key technical elements of the web environment have been defined in autumn 2017 in close cooperation between WP6 (data management system) and WP7. These involve specifically setting-up the technical interface between the data management system and the visual interface through APIs so that indicators can be extracted and fed to the visualization scripts. The programming of the visual elements was performed in spring 2018 and the visual interface was fully operational in September 2018.

7.2 Visualisation design

A consistent visual identity for the project has been defined, including logo, layouts for deliverables and presentations, selection of color and typographical elements. The visual identity will be adopted consistently for the web environment. The second step of the visualization design has taken place in spring 2018 and includes the graphical elements and the design for the tool.

7.3 User groups and user interaction

This task represented the main effort in the first project year. It involved the set-up of the user groups, the organization of two workshops with external users in Leiden and with Commission people in Brussels. The user groups have been further mobilized for testing purposes of the tool.

7.4 Pilot interface, development and testing

Based on the outcomes of task 7.3, work on the tool interface has started in autumn 2017 and led to basic design scenarios that have been proposed to a selected group of users in spring 2018 for validation. The results of this testing have been fed back in the tool development. The final testing phase has taken place in spring 2019 and fed back into the final release of the tool.

7.5 Usage and impact monitoring

The monitoring system is operational from M24 and includes indicators such as the number of users and accesses, as well as more detailed information on the type of usage and the indicators retrieved by users.

Short description of deliverables

D7.1 Report and online descriptions of usage scenarios. Status: delivered. This report has been delivered in first version at M6 and subsequently updated until M9. It includes an extensive analysis of user needs, elicited in terms of a set of user scenarios, that have been highly relevant to define the usage path of the KNOWMAK tool and have been also integrated in the KNOWMAK manual.

D7.2 Pilot Website and visualization environment. Status: delivered. This report shortly describes the KNOWMAK tool as it has been released in September 2018.

D7.3 Pilot testing event report. Status: delivered. This report describes the validation and testing of the KNOWMAK visualization environment by users and the implications for the tool.

D7.4 First impact monitoring report. Status: delivered. This report provides a first batch of statistics on the tool usage, including general statistics on usage, as well as more fine-grained statistics on the specific functionalities used.

D7.5 Full website and visualization environment. Status: delivered. This report provides a description of the KNOWMAK web interface and its functionalities in their final version.

D7.6 Blog entry with standardized views and results. Status: delivered. This report presents the seven data stories that have been published on the tool to illustrate its usages and added value.

D7.7 Infographics poster. Status: delivered. This poster summarizes the main elements of the KNOWMAK tools and derived indicators.

D7.8 Final impact monitoring report. Status: delivered. This report provides evidence on the usage of the tool and on its impact to different user communities.

Milestones

MS20. User groups constituted. Status: achieved.

MS21. Pilot Website delivered. Status: achieved.

MS22. Pilot website tested. Status: planned.

1.2.8 Work package 8. Dissemination

WP leader: AIT.

WP objectives: the objectives of WP7 are to:

- Design respective dissemination and communication activities and channels,
- Implement them using the most relevant, classical and newly developed communication channels,
- Design of a business model to ensure sustainability of the KNOWMAK tool.

Tasks and activities

8.1. Presentations at conferences, workshops and stakeholders

The project concept and specific activities (particularly ontology) was presented at numerous conferences and events in 2018; this activity has been fully operational in 2019 with several presentations at scientific conferences, such as EU-SPRI, STI and Atlanta in the US, as well as at stakeholders' events, such as the EARMA general assembly.

8.2 Design and implementation of communication activities

Nine editions of the newsletter have been published, mostly focused on the presentation of project results and analysis stories; a series of blog posts has been also posted on the project twitter account. These activities have by large reached the project targets.

8.3 Organization and implementation of training workshops

Three training workshops have been delivered in 2019, mostly to policymakers and policy analysts.

8.4 Business plan development and innovation management

An executive business plan has been developed, which foresees the integration of the KNOWMAK tool within RISIS2. The plan is being now implemented.

Short description of deliverables

D8.1 Dissemination executive plan (M12). Status: delivered. The dissemination plan describes in detail the communication activities for the project that will start in spring 2018 and will be mostly developed after the launch of the tool at M18.

D8.2 Report on dissemination activities. Status: delivered. This report presents the dissemination activities undertaken in the project, as compared with the original objectives.

D8.3 Draft business plan (M24). Status: delivered. This deliverable describes the plans for long-term maintenance and development of the KNOWMAK tool.

D8.4 Executive business plan. Status: delivered. This deliverable presents an executive plan for the integration of the KNOWMAK tool within RISIS2 and for the future development of the tool.

Milestones

MS25. Newsletter and social media accounts (M8). Status: achieved

1.2.9 Work package 9. Ethics requirements

WP leader: UPEM.

WP objectives: to ensure compliance with the 'ethics requirements' set out in this work package.

Tasks and activities

Following ethical issues have been identified and addressed:

- Potential data protection issues related to the integration of data sources that might make individuals identifiable by combining different data, particularly when the corresponding numbers are not very large. It has been clarified that all data provided by KNOWMAK come from public sources and data will be presented in the tool aggregated by organization, region and topic; therefore, there are no relevant issue concerning data protection.
- Data protection issues concerning new data collected about social innovation and citizen's attention collected from Internet sources and from twitter accounts. Approval hat been requested from the ethics commission at UMAN and USFD; both confirmed that no data protection issues are raised since all data come from public sources and will be anonymized.
- Ethical issues concerning the involvement of users for the design and testing of the KNOWMAK tool. The ZSI ethical committee confirmed that no ethical issues are involved, but suitable data protection measures need to be taken for personal data (for example account numbers).

Short description of deliverables.

D9.1. Ethical requirements. Submitted.

1.3 Impact

The KNOWMAK project has established a tool, providing interactive visualisation of state-of-the-art indicators on knowledge co-creation in the European research area. The tool was developed in a co-design approach to the needs of four groups: policy-makers at the European and national level, regional actors and representatives of civil society, representatives from the business sector and managers of public research organisations and universities.

→ The KNOWMAK dissemination activities are described in detail in *D7.1 Report on usage scenarios*.

The main project impact lies in the provision of a more effective basis for evidence-based policy and decision making in the EU. Users can gain novel insights into the driving forces about knowledge production, co-creation and cooperation for societal challenges or key enabling technologies. Further, the tool allows actors at local and regional levels to identify possible research partners and peers across European countries and regions, and enrich the knowledge base of research managers upon which research investment decisions are taken.

Given that impact requires time, the project focus has been on a) developing tool features that enable such impact and b) disseminating the tool in order to become used by the target user groups. The tool had about 2,500 visits in 2019 and between 150 and 200 unique visitors per month, a number, which is fairly high given the fact that the tool was launched only in fall 2018; visitors come from various European countries, but a fairly high number (more than 150) came from the US as well (most likely associated with the dissemination event at the Atlanta Science and Innovation conference in fall 2019). The usage statistics of the tool demonstrate that a significant share of the users switch between indicators and select topics; some recently introduced features, particularly the country and regional factsheets, also attracted significant interest.

→ A more complete analysis of the envisaged impacts and evidence to which extent they have been reached is provided in deliverable *D7.8 Final impact monitoring report*.

Among the six direct impacts foreseen by the project, there is already evidence that the tool is reaching two impacts, namely improved evidence-based policy-making and novel research opportunities for scientists. For the former, there has been high interest by policy analysts, while for the latter first analytical papers using KNOWMAK have been produced by the project team. The four other impacts foreseen by the description of work - effective research investment by research performers, stimulation of knowledge flows across Europe, novel partner search for research actors and improved policy design for RFOs - are all enabled by the tool features, but will be more long-term.

Furthering impact will be a core priority of the integration of the KNOWMAK tool within RISIS2 (see section 3.1). On the one hand, RISIS2 has a dedicated unit for dissemination that will also address systematically the KNOWMAK user communities; on the other hand, embedding in a broader data infrastructure for

science will generate additional opportunities for impact, for example combining insights from the KNOWMAK tool with more detailed data from other RISIS datasets.

2 Update of the plan for exploitation and dissemination of result

The plan for exploitation and dissemination of the project, as described in deliverable D8.1 Dissemination executive plan, has been fulfilled as planned (targets have been over fulfilled for most dissemination activities, e.g. website visits, newsletter recipients or social media engagements, while it has been slightly below the target for a few channels, e.g. blog posts). Accordingly, updates of the plan have tackled mainly the already started and ongoing integration of KNOWMAK dissemination activities into the RISIS dissemination universe (<https://www.risis2.eu>), where different activities, e.g. re-branding or presentation of KNOWMAK at the RISIS policymakers' session have taken place after M30 of the KNOWMAK project.

The KNOWMAK dissemination strategy has been set up along three general lines:

- *Awareness raising* activities
- *Training*: Making the users fit to effectively utilize the tool
- *Monitoring usage* and system adaption based on user needs

For these three lines, we have established different communication and dissemination channels (e.g. web site, social media activities, stakeholder events, trainings, etc.). In the first dissemination year (2018), the focus was on awareness raising activities, while additionally training and monitoring was the focus of the last project year (2019). KNOWMAK has set up three trainings (Italy, Austria and Belgium), and intensively promoted the KNOWMAK *data stories* (accessible directly on the entry page of the tool under www.knowmak.eu) that gives users example application for real-world policy questions, and how they can be addressed using the tool. After the launch of the tool, six data stories have been produced and promoted via the KNOWMAK dissemination channels and at conferences and events. Training activities will also be followed up when maintaining the tool within RISIS (KNOWMAK data have already been used in the RISIS data science summer school).

Particular emphasis was devoted to widely communicate and present the launch of the pilot of the web-based tool in 2018, and a final presentation at the policymakers' event in Brussels at the end of the project. KNOWMAK dissemination has mainly been conducted via the following communication channels in that context:

- The KNOWMAK web site www.knowmak.eu (online since January 2018)
- The KNOWMAK newsletter (9 issues between February 2018 and December 2019) and the KNOWMAK twitter account.
- The KNOWMAK launch event in September 2018 and the RISIS policy makers session (<https://www.risis2.eu/event/policy-makers-sessions-knowmak/>) in December 2019

With the integration of KNOWMAK into RISIS, dissemination activities on the KNOWMAK tool will accordingly be followed up by RISIS with existing resources. This tackles the newsletter and twitter account as well as the KNOWMAK data stories. Activities in this direction have already been initiated by the end of 2019.

→ The KNOWMAK dissemination activities are described in detail in *D8.2 Report on dissemination activities and tool impact*.

3 Update of the data management plan

The data management plan of the project, as described in deliverable D1.2 Data management plan final, is still by large valid; it has however to be seen in the context of the future development of the KNOWMAK tool within the H2020 RISIS - Research infrastructure for research and innovation policy studies H2020 project.

We shortly detail below the steps for the integration of KNOWMAK within RISIS2 and the implication for the business plan and data management plan.

3.1 Integration of KNOWMAK within the RISIS2 infrastructure

To define a viable business plan for the long-term maintenance of the RISIS tool, a SWOT analysis has been performed. The main conclusion is that the KNOWMAK tool really shows a unique selling proposition in terms of the combined provision of indicators on knowledge creation coming from different data sources in one place, and the presentation of these indicators across relevant integrative dimension, i.e. actors, geography and topics. At the same time, one major strength concerns its flexible design, enabling KNOWMAK to integrate effectively both new indicators, but also potential other relevant topical breakdowns.

However, from a maintenance and sustainability perspective, the major weaknesses refer to the rather large investment and also running costs of the tool. Against this background, it becomes rather clear that the KNOWMAK tool cannot be run as a fully private, self-sustained commercially oriented service. Not only the cost arguments and the business environment are striking, but KNOWMAK per se is clearly devoted to open science, and originally not set up as tool for profit.

Therefore, the consortium has developed a hybrid model, which is based on three pillars:

- *Public baseline (research) funding*: Refers to public funding sources from funders that have inherent interest in maintenance of the tool, as provided by the EU funded Research Infrastructure for Research and Innovation Policy Studies (RISIS). Since all source dataset owners and service providers (e.g. annotation services) are also part of RISIS, RISIS as a project has high interest in the maintenance of datasets and services per se.
- *In-kind contribution of dataset owners*: Though in this model, parts of the maintenance of source datasets are covered by public baseline funding (RISIS), remaining costs are only to be covered by in-kind contributions of source dataset owners, both in form of personnel working on maintenance and updates, and in form of overheads (office, computers, etc.).
- *Indirect contracting*: This refers to the utilization of the underlying KNOWMAK data that are not publicly available via indicators in the tool for contracted research, e.g. in tenders from public authorities, RFOs and/or companies. In indirect contracting, users requiring specific extractions will contract with one

of the RISIS2 partners, and this contract will include a specific return to support the KNOWMAK infrastructure.

To implement this model, the KNOWMAK central database and tool will be handed over to the RISIS2 project for further maintenance and development; ruling of IP rights within KNOWMAK is made simpler by the fact that all KNOWMAK partners but one are also RISIS2 partners; with the remaining partner a suitable a solution through a subcontracting agreement will be sought.

Based on these cornerstones, a detailed plan has been worked out for handing over the KNOWMAK tool to RISIS2, including few changes in the RISIS2 grant agreement that will be discussed at the RISIS2 General Assembly in January 2020.

→ The KNOWMAK integration within RISIS is described in more detail in *D8.4 Executive business plan*.

3.2 Update of the data management plan

In the perspective of the hand-over of the KNOWMAK tool to the RISIS2 project, the management of the KNOWMAK data will be handled as follows.

The data produced by KNOWMAK can be decomposed in the following categories.

a) The aggregated data that supports research results and documents produced by the project. This data is usually a specific extraction and combination of aggregated data from primary and secondary sources. All results from the project will be archived in the ZENODO repository within the RISIS community space (<https://zenodo.org/communities/risis/?page=1&size=20>) so that they are openly accessible to users.

b) The basic data sources that are mobilized for building KNOWMAK information and have a process of their own for updating and maintenance. This corresponds to four datasets that are part of the RISIS2 project (CWTS publication database, RISIS patent database, RISIS-EUPRO and RISISI-ESID); their periodic updating and maintenance is part of the RISIS2 grant agreement; these data will be available under 'controlled access mode' through the RISIS Central Facility (RCF). The two organizational registers OrgReg and FirmReg will also be further maintained and extended within RISIS and will be accessible to users through the RCF.

c) The secondary data is the extraction and first-level aggregation of primary data to build the 'KNOWMAK database'. This data is produced through stabilised routines that guarantee its periodic updating in connection with the maintenance and updating of primary data. The RISIS grant agreement will be amended to include the duty for data source owners to regularly update the KWNOMAK central database, as well as the maintenance of the central database by the Austrian Institute of Technology. Since the database has the sole function of feeding indicators into the tool, it will not be accessible to external users.

d) New software and tools developed within the KNOWMAK project. This includes:

- The ontology and the tools for its development and for the annotation of data sources. The maintenance and further updating of the ontology will be part of

RISIS2 activities, the specific ontology task is RISIS2 will be amended to this goal. Both the ontology and the tool are freely accessible via Sheffield platform, GATE (<https://gate.ac.uk/projects/knowmak/>).

- The geocoding software: the new software (UPEM) is freely accessible from GITHUB (<https://github.com/cortext/>). It has been integrated into the RISIS-CORTEXT facility, and is freely accessible to all users.
- The visualization software supporting the KNOWMAK tool. This software has been developed using open source tools and the corresponding development are also released open source (@Dietmar link). Their maintenance will be ensured through a RISIS additional subcontract to the KNOWMAK partner, who has developed the software.
- All the services that enable extracting and enriching data from the primary sources and the registers to build the KNOWMAK integrated database are only internal to the RISIS2 project. These will be maintained within RISIS2 as part of the RISIS Central Facility.

→ The KNOWMAK data management plan is described in *D1.2 Final Data Management Plan*.

4 Follow-up of recommendations and comments from previous review(s)

The project review took place the 1st of March 2018 by three external experts at the European Commission's premises in Brussels. As follow-up and taking into account the launch of the first version of the tool in September 2018, a distance review by the same experts was organized in November 2018.

We shortly summarize below the main recommendations from the experts and how they have been addressed in the following development of the project.

a) *Combining data and developing composite indicators*. In both reviews, the experts remarked that, while a strength of the project consisted in the integration of heterogeneous data sources through common integrative dimensions, actually the indicators available in the tool only referred to data sources individually, such as numbers of publications and of patents. The experts strongly advised the development of composite indicators.

To address this recommendation, the consortium performed extensive analyses of the statistical relationship between indicators in order to find robust ways of combining them. This eventually led to the provision in the tool of four indicators:

- The *knowledge production share*, defined as the mean of the share of a geographical space in the number of publications, patents and European projects.
- The *knowledge production intensity*, defined as the ratio between the previous indicator and the share of population of each geographical space.
- The *science production intensity* defined as the mean share of five indicators (number of publications; number of top 10% publications, number of international scientific publications, number of EU-participations and number of EU-FP coordination) relative to the share of population of in a geographical space.
- The *technology production intensity* defined as the mean share of two indicators (number of patent application and number of transnational patent applications) relative to the share of population of in a geographical space.

Statistical analysis showed that a) these indicators capture the main dimensions of knowledge production, as identified by the available indicators and b) these indicators can be reliably computed also at the level of individual KET and SGCs.

The project team considers that the data provided in KNOWMAK would allow for the development of additional synthetic indicators, such as specialisation indexes at the regional level; these indicators require, however, a more in-depth statistical analysis that became possible only once the ontology structure had been stabilized and full coverage of the whole period 2000-2016 had become available. It is likely that these indicators will be more useful for further analysis of data rather than in the tool itself. To address this task, a specific indicator development activity is introduced in the RISIS2 project as a follow-up of the KNOWMAK project (see also in section 2).

b) *Actors and their implementation in the tool.* The experts raised concerns on the extent of standardization of actors and the ensuing coverage of the European research landscape, particularly for firms.

This recommendation has been largely addressed for public research organizations thanks to the successive development of OrgReg, which currently includes over 6,000 organizations and cover all OrgReg countries. A final round of enrichment is on-going by extracting all public-sector organizations without an OrgReg identifier in the three main data sources and will be implemented in KNOWMAK during 2020.

As of firms, this recommendation was only partially implemented due to late implementation of the FirmReg RISIS facility. The focus was therefore on standardizing in KNWOMAK firms from the RISIS Corporate Innovation Board (RISIS-CIB), which includes the worldwide largest R&D corporate performers (about 4 000 parent companies and their 350 000 consolidated subsidiaries) that represent over 90% of world corporate industrial R&D. CIB firms are already included in FirmReg and matched with data sources; this process allowed the delivery of actor-level data for firms in KNOWMAK¹⁰. Further steps in the integration of firms will take place in 2020-2021 once the new version of FirmReg will become available.

c) *The ontology structure and extensions beyond KET and SGC.* The reviewers rightly pointed to the fact that KET and SGC might not fully represent the most relevant policy topics and might be replaced by other themes, such as the missions in Horizon Europe. As already highlighted in the response to the review, the KNOWMAK approach to the ontology is generic and can be extended to other topics than KET and SGC. At the same time, the KNOWMAK description of work explicitly mentions KET and SGCs.

Given this context and the fact that the final selection of missions will only take place during 2020, the project focused on the refinement of the current ontology, while performing some preliminary tests concerning the implementation of an ontology of the Horizon Europe mission. This task will be taken over in within the RISIS2 project and in the successive releases of the ontology foreseen in 2020 and 2021.

d) *Tool functionalities and deployment.* Concerns were expressed on the fact that the first version of the tool provided to users only limited functionalities, as actors were not yet visible, possibilities for scaling were limited to only the size of the population, and only one composite indicator was available. As discussed in this report, actors are now visible in the country/regional factsheets and additional composite indicators are currently available; scaling with GDP was not introduced as it would have made the tool too complex for users; this choice might be reconsidered within the RISIS project. Additionally, the tool has been substantially extended with the inclusion of more indicators (user attention, open access, network centrality), the country/regional factsheets and improved downloading options.

¹⁰ For patents, the process will be completed in spring 2020.

e) *Social innovation projects*. It was remarked that the production of indicators on social innovation might be quite challenging. This remark and the experimental nature of the ESID database led to change of approach: for what concerns social innovation, no indicators are provided, since the number of cases would be too low to have reliable figures; instead, individual social innovation projects (by space and topic) are displayed in the factsheets and users can consult some basic data on these projects, including a project description and link to a website. This also required a change in the development process of ESID by focusing to a stronger extent on the quality of the available information, which required adding a layer of manual checks upon the information retrieved automatically. At the same time, as a further indicator of societal outreach, the number of open access was added (not foreseen in the original description of work).

5 Deviations from Annex 1 and Annex 2

5.1 Tasks

Largely, the project has fulfilled the goal and tasks foreseen in the Description of Action. The main objective, i.e. the implementation of a fully operational tool providing information on knowledge production in the ERA, has been achieved.

We comment below on some minor deviations by work package.

WP1 (project coordination). Project coordination and report have been ensured smoothly, including the external review and changes in the consortium. The project was completed timely at M36, all deliverables have been finalised and milestones reached.

WP2 (ontology). All tasks have been completed as foreseen. The ontology is finalised and all data sources have been annotated.

WP3 (data source enhancement). All three data sources have been annotated with the ontology, actors' have been standardized and data items geolocalised. The only small departure is that firms' harmonization will be implemented for patent data in spring 2020.

WP4 (social innovation and user attention). The ESID database has been realised as foreseen; an important change has been to provide information on individual social innovation projects rather than indicators as explained in section 1.1.7. User attention indicators have been implemented as planned and an additional indicator of open access has been introduced.

WP5 (integrative methodology and tools). Actors' harmonization has been completed for public sectors and large firms. We have decided not to harmonize social innovation actors since data have shown they are very diffused. Indicators have been defined, including some composite indicators, and geolocalisation has been completed; additionally, a new regional classification has been implemented.

WP6 (data management system). The database and management systems are fully operational and provide a very robust and efficient environment for data extraction, indicator production and communication with the visual interface. The final user handbook is available on-line.

WP7 (user interaction and visualization). The visual interface for the KNWOAMK tool is now fully operational and has been testing by involving lead users. Usage and impact monitoring systems are operational.

WP8 (dissemination). Dissemination activities have been implemented as in the plan and the business plan finalised with the hand-over of the tool to the RISIS2 project.

WP (ethics). All potential ethical issues have been cleared.

5.2 Use of resources

No major deviation of the use of resources between actual and planned use of resources in Annex 1 has been found.

Nevertheless, there have been few small deviations between actual and planned use of resources as in Annex 1:

UPEM: The personal costs have be overspent (around 40,000€ more) as some senior staff have been more implicated than expected but the overall person-months (and per work package) is more or less the same. The cost for equipment has also been used for the rent of computer servers and the costs for travels has also been overspent. Adjustments to previous financial statements have been made as there has been a mistake in the personal costs calculation for M. Ospina Delgado and M. Lepori.

UNIMAN: The personal costs have be underspent (around 20.000€ more) but the overall person-months (and per work package) is more or less the same. The other direct costs have been overspent as the budget for M. Abdullah Gok (moving to Strathclyde University) has been left in Manchester for practical reasons.

STRATHCLYDE: The personal costs have been slightly underspent, while the budget for travel (2.000€) has not been used.

ZSI: The overall budget has been slightly underspent (around 4.000€ less) because of less user engagement workshops that expected and reallocation to the development of the tool (via personal costs). The budget for subcontracting has been slightly underspent too (1.800€ less)

5.2.1 Unforeseen subcontracting

No unforeseen subcontracting has taken place.

The only planned subcontracting was dedicated to the implementation of the visualisations interface, based on the conceptualisation and technical implementation (both performed by ZSI). This included support in the design of specific elements (overriding design concept, individual design items like icons, etc.), its implementation in the web environment (css stylesheets, etc.) and its exploitation for dissemination (infographics, etc.).

Out of 25.000€, 1.800€ remain unused.

5.2.2 Unforeseen use of in kind contribution from third party against payment or free of charges

No use of in kind contribution from third party against payment or free of charges has taken place.